

Circle packing inside an equilateral triangle: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 400$ congruent disks packed inside an equilateral triangle obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside an equilateral triangle that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 400$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside an equilateral triangle, for $2 \leq N \leq 400$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 400$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceeds by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is

large: configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside the equilateral triangle for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.316987298108	0.486006074879	41	0.0897723572184	0.799092577193
3	0.316987298108	0.729009112318	42	0.0892510848234	0.809103871873
4	0.250000000000	0.604599788078	43	0.0889884186696	0.823499645051
5	0.232050807569	0.651124676402	44	0.0889869382012	0.842622762063
6	0.232050807569	0.781349611682	45	0.0889869382012	0.861773279382
7	0.193997690458	0.637116923636	46	0.084376171281	0.792000476427
8	0.186366064712	0.671972713969	47	0.083660662138	0.795551749073
9	0.183012701892	0.729009112318	48	0.0829420209193	0.798580029168
10	0.183012701892	0.810010124798	49	0.0827615628781	0.811673615026
11	0.161420001163	0.693162978663	50	0.0815219673995	0.803613623238
12	0.158493649054	0.729009112318	51	0.0813405775582	0.816042281922
13	0.151847756732	0.724916683815	52	0.0807277100997	0.81955214771
14	0.151084739626	0.772853572096	53	0.0806952388982	0.834640923413
15	0.151084739626	0.828057398674	54	0.0806952388982	0.850388865364
16	0.136235754428	0.718174807623	55	0.0806952388982	0.866136807316
17	0.133974596216	0.737941299922	56	0.0770820915254	0.804679596185
18	0.130290125298	0.738964355741	57	0.0765968279489	0.808768834071
19	0.128795641995	0.762226281892	58	0.076200796593	0.814469823918
20	0.128642137224	0.800432052176	59	0.0755438223324	0.814287755176
21	0.128642137224	0.840453654785	60	0.075542369813	0.828057398674
22	0.118531600695	0.747513364062	61	0.0743982296417	0.816550444587
23	0.116380382903	0.753382245825	62	0.0740451897614	0.822078655613
24	0.116025403784	0.781349611682	63	0.0738188105761	0.830238020481
25	0.11325175364	0.775457251809	64	0.0738170519365	0.843376215585
26	0.11204202297	0.789338367484	65	0.0738170519365	0.856553968953
27	0.11200461887	0.819150331291	66	0.0738170519365	0.869731722322
28	0.11200461887	0.84948923245	67	0.0707890176172	0.811959851447
29	0.104305204935	0.763023548223	68	0.0703726229033	0.814412387932
30	0.103529091652	0.777631856942	69	0.0700381984832	0.818553379754
31	0.102317462994	0.784854589059	70	0.0696087205637	0.820263382559
32	0.100423336871	0.780453902089	71	0.0694815744067	0.828944839207
33	0.0995060017893	0.790206275909	72	0.0686757817882	0.821235476982
34	0.0991785193598	0.808801857134	73	0.0684772600256	0.827834632787
35	0.0991777788368	0.832577713916	74	0.0681735418193	0.831747332349
36	0.0991777788368	0.8563656486	75	0.0680193987987	0.839179417469
37	0.0934665296464	0.781703293642	76	0.0680193173019	0.850366438648
38	0.0924742938613	0.785875276153	77	0.0680193173019	0.861555470736
39	0.0915649399888	0.79077151923	78	0.0680193173019	0.872744502823
40	0.0915063509461	0.810010124798	79	0.0655533023176	0.821002013992

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside the equilateral triangle for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0651284100081	0.820651788875	121	0.0534892476644	0.837232987122
81	0.0648153798674	0.82294183788	122	0.0532652074406	0.837095597841
82	0.0644677944378	0.824190224608	123	0.0531099208215	0.839043353154
83	0.0643211950501	0.830451519019	124	0.0529192998836	0.839803822133
84	0.0643210686119	0.840453654785	125	0.0526988903456	0.839539116826
85	0.0635413088457	0.829963933531	126	0.052615983761	0.843594843986
86	0.0634594732153	0.837566615456	127	0.0526008296127	0.849800320554
87	0.0631985502636	0.840352442029	128	0.0521665799693	0.84240838769
88	0.0630778488012	0.846767930441	129	0.0520422628927	0.844948105771
89	0.0630659918114	0.856068365485	130	0.0520232080728	0.850874668064
90	0.0630659918114	0.865687111165	131	0.051763191956	0.848870372049
91	0.0630659918114	0.875305856844	132	0.0517590342798	0.855212898727
92	0.0609442182647	0.826381965242	133	0.0517584732287	0.861673103507
93	0.0607071663571	0.828878460091	134	0.0517584732287	0.868151848646
94	0.0603432884104	0.827777813989	135	0.0517584732287	0.874630593785
95	0.0602869998608	0.835023948686	136	0.0517584732287	0.881109338924
96	0.0598937450427	0.832841109552	137	0.0504242536953	0.842417746919
97	0.0598741233177	0.840965251449	138	0.0502477586323	0.842636867775
98	0.0592755981328	0.832733330181	139	0.0500484314542	0.842022553493
99	0.0591331971232	0.837193595508	140	0.0499102791822	0.843404698291
100	0.0589106657012	0.83929733224	141	0.0498717642269	0.848118542124
101	0.058791439721	0.84426259227	142	0.0496536187977	0.846677732016
102	0.0587851219831	0.852438391958	143	0.0495888894184	0.850418664929
103	0.058785121983	0.860795631092	144	0.0495888861515	0.856365535765
104	0.0587851219831	0.869152870232	145	0.0491398329544	0.846765852255
105	0.0587851219831	0.877510109369	146	0.0490752005891	0.850364271
106	0.0570079511254	0.833114537044	147	0.0489190122883	0.850747489374
107	0.0567304419524	0.832806475603	148	0.048918859124	0.856529523686
108	0.0565797333751	0.836129469677	149	0.0488395605535	0.859523481138
109	0.0563633474971	0.837429078366	150	0.0488395512275	0.865291764647
110	0.0560848770297	0.836781771778	151	0.0488395512275	0.871060376411
111	0.0560023094349	0.84190450716	152	0.0488395512275	0.876828988175
112	0.0560023094349	0.84948923245	153	0.0488395512275	0.88259759994
113	0.055410274069	0.839048416199	154	0.0476510986281	0.845657566109
114	0.0553480322471	0.84457302031	155	0.0474921848632	0.845481247171
115	0.0551503323028	0.845905968922	156	0.0473310213483	0.845170505118
116	0.0550493200286	0.850138900511	157	0.0472028420833	0.845987470447
117	0.0550484748859	0.857441355857	158	0.0471561736942	0.84969328539
118	0.0550484748859	0.864769914454	159	0.0469668805968	0.848220060582
119	0.0550484748859	0.872098473051	160	0.0469033075781	0.851245647393
120	0.0550484748859	0.879427031648	161	0.0469031949598	0.856561819337

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside the equilateral triangle for $162 \leq N \leq 243$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0465322458795	0.848303043262	203	0.0418025484817	0.857885916586
163	0.0464583480829	0.850830624685	204	0.0417724897357	0.86087257242
164	0.0464433804753	0.8554989413	205	0.0417744591913	0.8651741113
165	0.0462825753746	0.854765451695	206	0.0417722968036	0.869304469536
166	0.0462325954884	0.858089564942	207	0.0417722979564	0.873524442358
167	0.0462325411604	0.863256750354	208	0.0417722979662	0.877744367614
168	0.0462322785719	0.868416087624	209	0.0417722979662	0.881964292459
169	0.0462322792459	0.873585256476	210	0.0417722979662	0.886184217303
170	0.0462322792459	0.878754400005	211	0.0409500430575	0.855695331799
171	0.0462322792459	0.883923543535	212	0.0408288705566	0.854670227205
172	0.0451981606978	0.849763264863	213	0.0407279746218	0.85446290278
173	0.04503379171	0.848498569868	214	0.0406463704764	0.855037766816
174	0.0449518084854	0.850298803257	215	0.0405600830143	0.855389888621
175	0.0448571662614	0.85158832728	216	0.0405346706938	0.85829193439
176	0.0447211113377	0.851267052136	217	0.0403980606748	0.856463284511
177	0.0445746876445	0.850506947202	218	0.0403565227895	0.85864165667
178	0.0445060108613	0.852678521356	219	0.0403476194491	0.862199821828
179	0.0444934691006	0.856985650052	220	0.0403475957824	0.866135791216
180	0.0444934603554	0.86177294062	221	0.0400608602464	0.857750139534
181	0.0441456271327	0.853064635677	222	0.0400069027364	0.85931188232
182	0.0440794823799	0.855209156177	223	0.0399196944433	0.859423573219
183	0.0439469967353	0.854746782356	224	0.0398906774457	0.862022941067
184	0.04390994657	0.857969051328	225	0.0398503850965	0.86412296119
185	0.0438932522761	0.861976116505	226	0.0398501462864	0.867953104882
186	0.0438902400838	0.866516504526	227	0.0398501444903	0.871793526762
187	0.0438892749786	0.871136883178	228	0.0398501462864	0.87563410581
188	0.0438892749786	0.875795369185	229	0.0398501462618	0.879474605191
189	0.0438892749786	0.880453855191	230	0.0398501450541	0.883315052109
190	0.0438892749786	0.885112341197	231	0.0398501462864	0.887155607202
191	0.0429567401476	0.852361809274	232	0.0391014998656	0.85783310018
192	0.0428491873971	0.852539266879	233	0.0389508847973	0.854906379374
193	0.0427337222985	0.852367216917	234	0.0388987574427	0.856279007075
194	0.0426481344361	0.853355101055	235	0.0387936632183	0.855297941206
195	0.0425298763122	0.853003538322	236	0.0387227011604	0.855798013456
196	0.0425250873396	0.857184840431	237	0.0387222701988	0.859405146526
197	0.0423663517298	0.855138270308	238	0.0385905890206	0.857171561177
198	0.042319274943	0.857570057176	239	0.038589415984	0.860720793379
199	0.0423192486077	0.861900146358	240	0.0385515237808	0.862625556925
200	0.0420350213345	0.854634699671	241	0.0385515133098	0.866219359531
201	0.0419802991894	0.856673037257	242	0.038289627687	0.858036247427
202	0.041944524397	0.859468373194	243	0.038215202016	0.858235698201

Table 4: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside the equilateral triangle for $244 \leq N \leq 325$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
244	0.0382403223396	0.862900850669	285	0.0354066882002	0.864059112978
245	0.0380979606151	0.859998162488	286	0.0353998177276	0.866754423569
246	0.0380981854428	0.863518550753	287	0.0353998419549	0.86978622399
247	0.038097123842	0.866980470159	288	0.035166620054	0.861354105865
248	0.0380971076566	0.870489772897	289	0.0351666405637	0.864345926927
249	0.038097107242	0.873999793284	290	0.0350689802867	0.862526119911
250	0.0380971069563	0.877509819451	291	0.0351372815273	0.868874972075
251	0.0380971076675	0.881019891621	292	0.0350185820846	0.865980171689
252	0.0380971074669	0.884529921718	293	0.0350163866884	0.868836908154
253	0.0380971080568	0.888039988588	294	0.0350163198199	0.871798892193
254	0.0374294262969	0.860573640637	295	0.0350163193628	0.874764171706
255	0.0373109544079	0.858501145745	296	0.0350163178232	0.877729396799
256	0.0372212258916	0.857727417285	297	0.0350163173015	0.880694672576
257	0.0371459068828	0.857596572616	298	0.0350163184906	0.883660034518
258	0.0370819747795	0.857972556034	299	0.035016318527	0.886625338488
259	0.0370649887778	0.860509148634	300	0.0350163199373	0.889590712285
260	0.037064977201	0.863831038166	301	0.0344647097319	0.86465673335
261	0.0369239114649	0.860565420601	302	0.0343499740372	0.861762816591
262	0.036915873438	0.863486535719	303	0.0342747258365	0.860832370173
263	0.0369084987364	0.866436005429	304	0.0342306966247	0.86145588171
264	0.0369085134054	0.869731130247	305	0.0341977353982	0.862625945911
265	0.0366517204401	0.860919582799	306	0.0341424759535	0.862659546699
266	0.0366232240473	0.862825091645	307	0.0341424709893	0.86547844387
267	0.0365266971697	0.861509461459	308	0.0340400913148	0.863098041872
268	0.0365258432461	0.864695657411	309	0.034021465487	0.864952972501
269	0.0364936235416	0.866391608586	310	0.034009658651	0.86714998678
270	0.0364921396628	0.869541677503	311	0.0340096440617	0.869946498433
271	0.0364918063564	0.872746259302	312	0.0340096495436	0.872744035402
272	0.0364918047762	0.875966649336	313	0.0337763326514	0.863569521071
273	0.0364918064101	0.87918719369	314	0.0336963263558	0.862229229924
274	0.0364918064101	0.882407659601	315	0.0336844389169	0.864364996137
275	0.0364918064101	0.885628125512	316	0.0336558641512	0.865638485654
276	0.0364918064101	0.888848591423	317	0.0336712264292	0.869170774047
277	0.0358790653516	0.862362759051	318	0.0336555142626	0.871099097957
278	0.0357607921751	0.859779407887	319	0.0336555142942	0.873838404937
279	0.0357061281772	0.860236180614	320	0.0336555125107	0.876577617374
280	0.0356675102643	0.861453030367	321	0.0336555142946	0.879317015645
281	0.0356037475657	0.86144137725	322	0.03365551312	0.882056259422
282	0.0355437740939	0.861596984368	323	0.0336555140418	0.884795613043
283	0.0355437459458	0.864650923341	324	0.0336555142946	0.887534931682
284	0.0354151377191	0.861438330022	325	0.0336555131941	0.890274178805

Table 5: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside the equilateral triangle for $326 \leq N \leq 400$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
326	0.0331456322726	0.866160147495	364	0.0315327880821	0.875294319173
327	0.0330413478988	0.863358653054	365	0.0313306383959	0.866481580082
328	0.0329748600834	0.862517168601	366	0.0313244417203	0.868511846071
329	0.0329581813874	0.864271832339	367	0.0313045412585	0.869778632046
330	0.0329105640703	0.864395652076	368	0.0312289375671	0.867941030671
331	0.0328474676693	0.863693723178	369	0.031250921459	0.871525307801
332	0.0328473627052	0.866297533236	370	0.0312285004006	0.872633669393
333	0.0328474856628	0.868913368331	371	0.0312284611522	0.874989939367
334	0.0327376595659	0.86570456016	372	0.0312283196443	0.877340451644
335	0.0327303519963	0.867908897895	373	0.0312283216532	0.879699006897
336	0.0327245344043	0.870190247729	374	0.0312283216915	0.882057451439
337	0.0327245160267	0.872779119373	375	0.0312283203649	0.88441581868
338	0.0325334096794	0.865174770522	376	0.0312283185601	0.886774158366
339	0.0325088153881	0.866422992143	377	0.0312283216915	0.88913277859
340	0.0324281102319	0.864669579899	378	0.0312283216915	0.891491220973
341	0.0324375400879	0.867717157221	379	0.0307446738315	0.866377114711
342	0.0323971424979	0.86809549062	380	0.0307005777769	0.86617306848
343	0.0323965859304	0.870603867638	381	0.0306602673568	0.866173380565
344	0.0323965180691	0.873138413385	382	0.0306079262715	0.865484227937
345	0.032396519422	0.875676679585	383	0.0305859162534	0.866502352305
346	0.032396517564	0.878214772126	384	0.0305500071951	0.866726030604
347	0.0323965176432	0.880752969414	385	0.0305313937553	0.867924548046
348	0.0323965178225	0.883291172191	386	0.0304757902929	0.86701226183
349	0.0323965194447	0.885829453926	387	0.0304521820209	0.867912175703
350	0.0323965194447	0.888367647204	388	0.0304285778692	0.868806413563
351	0.0323965194447	0.890905840482	389	0.0304251795997	0.870851059127
352	0.0318960002239	0.866050260821	390	0.0304251623392	0.87308876017
353	0.0318225855876	0.864517151307	391	0.0304251501623	0.875326748643
354	0.0317952230977	0.865475936321	392	0.0302479537361	0.867373299735
355	0.0317378843423	0.864793230478	393	0.030223785447	0.868196933462
356	0.0317113726916	0.865781025241	394	0.0301807190431	0.867927339323
357	0.0316474858442	0.864718253374	395	0.030146065674	0.868133188375
358	0.0316470915391	0.867118825588	396	0.0301420580419	0.870099604877
359	0.031588420254	0.866319809157	397	0.0301414472654	0.8722614753
360	0.0315579510873	0.867057861189	398	0.0301414397842	0.874458173394
361	0.0315375016779	0.868339899819	399	0.0301414374747	0.876655170136
362	0.031532948896	0.870493888514	400	0.0301414381104	0.878852337962
363	0.0315329919809	0.872900953132			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($194 \leq N \leq 205$).

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($206 \leq N \leq 217$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($218 \leq N \leq 229$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($230 \leq N \leq 241$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($242 \leq N \leq 253$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($254 \leq N \leq 265$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($266 \leq N \leq 277$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($278 \leq N \leq 289$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($290 \leq N \leq 301$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($302 \leq N \leq 313$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($314 \leq N \leq 325$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($326 \leq N \leq 337$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($338 \leq N \leq 349$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($350 \leq N \leq 361$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($362 \leq N \leq 373$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($374 \leq N \leq 385$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($386 \leq N \leq 397$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($398 \leq N \leq 400$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of a pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 35: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 36: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 37: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 38: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 39: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 40: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 41: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 42: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 43: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 44: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 45: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 46: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 47: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 48: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 49: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 50: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 51: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($194 \leq N \leq 205$).

Figure 52: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($206 \leq N \leq 217$).

Figure 53: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($218 \leq N \leq 229$).

Figure 54: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($230 \leq N \leq 241$).

Figure 55: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($242 \leq N \leq 253$).

Figure 56: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($254 \leq N \leq 265$).

Figure 57: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($266 \leq N \leq 277$).

Figure 58: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($278 \leq N \leq 289$).

Figure 59: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($290 \leq N \leq 301$).

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Figure 61: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($314 \leq N \leq 325$).

Figure 62: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($326 \leq N \leq 337$).

Figure 63: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($338 \leq N \leq 349$).

Figure 64: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($350 \leq N \leq 361$).

Figure 65: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($362 \leq N \leq 373$).

Figure 66: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($374 \leq N \leq 385$).

Figure 67: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($386 \leq N \leq 397$).

Figure 68: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($398 \leq N \leq 400$).

Acknowledgements

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References

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- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>